

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Computers & Education

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/compedu

“Digital constructivists, activators or presenters? Different profiles of technology integration among swiss upper secondary school teachers”^{☆, ☆ ☆}

Chiara Antonietti^{a,b,*}, Tessa Consoli^a, Maria-Luisa Schmitz^a, Alberto Cattaneo^b, Philipp Gonon^a, Dominik Petko^a

^a Institute of Education, University of Zurich (UZH), Freiestrasse 36, 8032, Zurich, Switzerland

^b Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET), via Besso 84, 6900, Lugano, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Technology integration
Upper secondary schools
Technological knowledge
Teachers' beliefs about technology
Latent profile analysis

ABSTRACT

This study explores patterns of technology integration in upper secondary school learning activities. Data were collected via an online survey in Switzerland. Through latent profile analysis, three distinct teacher profiles emerged. Teachers in Profile 1 (*digital presenters*; N = 896) mainly integrated technology to present content; Profile 2 (*digital activators*; N = 979) used technology for presentation and allowed students to interact with materials; Profile 3 (*digital constructivists*; N = 213) emphasized student interaction with technology to generate new knowledge over presenting content. Additionally, we investigated how teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK) and positive beliefs about technology predict profile membership. The results showed that TPCK and positive beliefs are associated with belonging to a profile. This study outlines distinct technology integration profiles among teachers and highlights the role of TPCK and beliefs in shaping these practices.

1. Introduction

The integration of technology into education has grown significantly, and, consequently, the research related to this theme (Tamim et al., 2011; Valtonen et al., 2022). Whereas many previous large-scale survey studies, such as the International Computer and Information Literacy Study and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study, have focused mainly on the frequency of technology use in class, recent research has shifted the focus toward understanding how technology is integrated into learning activities by teachers (Antonietti et al., 2023; Fütterer et al., 2022; Juuti et al., 2022; Petko et al., 2017). Indeed, the potential for technology to enhance teaching and learning depends mainly on how it is pedagogically integrated to support activities that engage students in the classroom (OECD, 2015; Stegmann, 2020; Wekerle et al., 2020). When its affordances are recognized and leveraged, technology can be a facilitator of changing instructional practice at school, leading to a shift from a teacher-directed to a

* Given the significant contributions made by Chiara Antonietti and Tessa Consoli to this research endeavor, we kindly request the implementation of a share-first co-authorship arrangement to appropriately recognize their efforts.** This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (grant number 187277).

* Corresponding author. Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET) via Besso 84, 6900, Lugano, Switzerland.
E-mail addresses: chiara.antonietti@suffp.swiss (C. Antonietti), tessa.consoli@ife.uzh.ch (T. Consoli), maria-luisa.schmitz@ife.uzh.ch (M.-L. Schmitz), alberto.cattaneo@suffp.swiss (A. Cattaneo), gonon@ife.uzh.ch (P. Gonon), dominik.petko@uzh.ch (D. Petko).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2024.105225>

Received 20 June 2024; Received in revised form 13 December 2024; Accepted 13 December 2024

Available online 14 December 2024

0360-1315/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

student-centered style of teaching, in which students take more responsibility for their learning and in which classroom activities include more knowledge building, problem-solving, discussion, and cooperative and collaborative learning (Callahan, 2001; Jeong & Hmelo-Silver, 2016; Johnson & Johnson, 2013).

To understand the impact of technology integration on learning, it is, therefore, necessary to differentiate and examine the types of learning activities supported by the use of technology. In the present study, we investigate the use of digital technologies by teachers and students through the lens of the interactive-constructive-active-passive (ICAP) theory of active learning (Chi et al., 2018; Chi & Wylie, 2014). ICAP is a theoretical model that classifies learning activities by levels of engagement: *passive* (P), *active* (A), *constructive* (C), *interactive* (I). *Passive* engagement involves receiving information rather than actively processing or applying it, while *Active* (A) engagement emphasizes hands-on, participatory activities that require learners to apply the information imparted by the teacher. *Constructive* (C) engagement requires learners actively build their own understanding of the instructional and involves activities such as solving complex problems, critical thinking, and applying knowledge to create new insights or infer new knowledge. *Interactive* (I) engagement involves discussions and interactions among learners and the co-construction of their knowledge. The theory suggests that higher engagement leads to better learning outcomes. In technology education research, ICAP helps differentiate activities supported by technology based on their potential to engage learners (Antonietti et al., 2023; Ninković et al., 2023; Sailer et al., 2021; Wekerle et al., 2020). This model enables a more detailed analysis of technology integration in classroom activities, beyond simply assessing the frequency of digital tool use.

In the present study, we apply latent profile analysis to assess technology integration by upper secondary teachers across ICAP learning activities, unveiling distinct profiles that capture nuanced patterns in teaching practices. Examining the heterogeneity of technology integration is of particular interest because it unveils the intricate dynamics shaping the educational landscape and offers valuable insights into the varied approaches to technology integration. After identifying teachers' profiles, we explore differences between profiles in terms of self-assessed technological pedagogical content knowledge levels and attitudes toward the use of technology for teaching and learning, as these proved to be two fundamental factors supporting technology integration in education (Antonietti et al., 2022; Backfisch et al., 2021; Cattaneo et al., 2022; Lucas et al., 2021). This investigation provides insights into the relationship between instructional strategies involving technology, teachers' technological knowledge, and attitudes, offering an understanding of the factors influencing different patterns of technology integration in education.

2. Conceptual background

This section reviews studies using latent or cluster profile analysis to examine technology use and situate our study within educational technology research. Additionally, we outline technology integration and teacher training in Switzerland.

2.1. Profiles of technology integration in education

Adopting profile analysis in the study of technology integration in schools is valuable for capturing the diverse approaches that teachers employ when using technology for educational purposes. Profiling offers a detailed examination, uncovers distinct patterns, and sheds light on the multifaceted nature of teachers' technology integration strategies. This method surpasses traditional methods (e.g., descriptive analysis) by providing a more comprehensive understanding of the varied ways in which technology is integrated into teaching practices. Identifying unique profiles provides valuable insights into the complexity of instructional practices, enabling the design of targeted interventions and tailored support for educators.

The investigation of the different ways in which technology is used in education has a long tradition. In the 1990s, Hadley and Sheingold (1993) analyzed patterns of computer use in the classroom and described five different teachers' profiles of technology integration based on how technology is used by teachers and teachers' beliefs: enthusiastic beginners, supported integrators, high school naturals, unsupported achievers, and struggling aspirers. However, these findings are outdated, as they relate only to the use of computers, whereas many new technologies have since been introduced in schools (e.g., mobile devices).

Donnelly et al. (2011) interviewed thirteen Irish science educators and proposed the teacher information and communications technology integration model, categorizing teachers into four groups based on empowerment vs. fatalism and teacher-directed vs. student-centered approaches: contented traditionalist, selective adopter, inadvertent user, and creative adapter. Mama and Hennessy (2013) studied the technology use and beliefs of eleven Cypriot teachers, identifying four groups (A, B, C, and D). Group A, the high users, integrated diverse technologies aligned with lesson objectives and viewed technology as a differentiation tool, while Group D, the low users, were more resistant to technology integration. While these qualitative studies provide detailed insights into technology integration, their small sample sizes limit the generalizability of the findings.

Graves and Bowers (2018) analyzed data from a 2009 national survey of the use of educational technology by over two thousand teachers in US public schools. Using latent class analysis, they identified four groups of technology-using teachers. The *presenters* group (24.8%) preferred using technology for classroom presentations but rarely utilized it for drill-and-practice tasks, problem-solving, or creating digital media. The *assessor* group (28.4%) favored using drill-and-practice software, guiding students to practice basic skills in subjects like mathematics and literacy. The *dexterous* group (24.4%) consisted of flexible teachers who used technology in various ways, such as preparing lessons, guiding students in writing, conducting research, creating multimedia presentations, and performing experiments. The *evaders* group (22.2%) resisted using technology entirely, neither incorporating it into their teaching nor allowing students to use it for learning activities, assessments, or practice. Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al. (2021) qualitatively explored university faculty members' integration of mobile technologies, such as tablets, in teaching and learning activities. A latent profile analysis identified five profiles based on self-reported knowledge, self-efficacy, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and attitudes

toward mobile technology. Faculty members were categorized into five profiles: *technology enthusiasts* (28.3%), who were highly knowledgeable and enthusiastic about using mobile technology in classrooms; *knowledgeable adopters* (32.8%), who demonstrated high knowledge, self-efficacy, and positive attitudes; *knowledgeable skeptics* (19.3%), who had high knowledge but low perceived usefulness; *prospective adopters* (9.9%), who showed low knowledge and self-efficacy but held positive attitudes; and *non-adopters* (9.6%), who scored low across all dimensions.

In higher education, Lohr et al. (2021) examined technology use in learning activities based on the ICAP model, identifying three clusters of teacher-initiated digital learning activities. The *powerpointers* (n = 483) were teachers who primarily used technology for passive learning, such as digitally supported presentations or video/audio materials. The *clickers* (n = 477) used technology for both passive and active learning, incorporating digital presentations alongside tools like audience-response systems, digital quizzes, and worksheets to foster active engagement. The *digital pros* (n = 437) reported high technology use across various ICAP learning activities. In addition to presentations and active learning tools, they utilized technology for problem-solving, idea generation, and evaluative tasks in both individual and collaborative settings.

Unlike earlier research, Lohr et al. (2021) focused on how technology is integrated in different learning activities, using the ICAP theory to profile teachers' technology integration. The adoption of a theoretical model for the study of technology integration endows this study with higher scientific relevance than previous studies. However, as with several other studies that used the ICAP framework to measure technology integration quality (see also Ninković et al., 2023), Lohr et al. (2021) used a combination of quantitative and qualitative information, without distinguish between the frequency of technology integration (i.e., how often technology is used in different ICAP modes) and the quality of technology integration (i.e., the relative distribution or balance of different types of technology-supported activities in these modes). Looking at information about the quality and quantity together does not allow a clear distinction between pedagogical patterns of technology use and the frequency of a specific use of technology.

Since several studies have shown that the quality of technology integration is more important than the frequency of technology integration (Juuti et al., 2022; Petko et al., 2017), we focused on the relative frequencies of technology integration across different ICAP modes, deliberately excluding information related to the absolute frequency of technology use from the data. For example, we expect a teacher who integrates digital technologies only twice a week, with 50% of the time in the active modality and 50% of the time in the constructive modality, to have the same ICAP score as a teacher who integrates digital technologies several times a day with the same time allocation in the active and constructive modes. If, instead, we consider the absolute frequency of technology integration across ICAP modes, these two teachers would be placed in two different classes. This shift in emphasis does not imply that the issue of frequency is irrelevant; rather, it suggests that the quality of integration should be the primary concern. Given that previous studies have predominantly concentrated on the absolute frequency of integration, this investigation aims to delve deeper into the qualitative aspects of technology integration in classroom. Conversely, this approach also has disadvantages, as considering the relative frequency only allows us to overlook the quantitative aspects. Indeed, a teacher who does not utilize technology except sometimes for transmissive activities (i.e., passive learning activities) is comparable to a teacher who employs technology sometimes for a range of activities (e.g., active, constructive, or interactive learning activities) and very often for transmissive activities. While the two teachers exhibit similar patterns of technology use, they differ significantly in terms of the overall frequency of technology use in the classroom. The choice to focus on either frequency or quality of technology integration has both advantages and disadvantages. In this study, we prioritized quality in order to identify meaningful patterns of technology use, rather than simply measuring how often it is employed; however, further research should integrate both aspects.

Despite their shortcomings, previous studies highlight the advantages of adopting a person-centered approach in describing technology integration by teachers. First, cluster and latent profile analysis allow for the identification of distinct clusters or profiles of teachers based on their technology integration practices. For example, this approach allowed Graves and Bowers (2018) to reach their goal of exploring if there are underlying subgroups of similar technology users. This person-centered approach avoids the assumption that teachers are uniform in their technology use and goes beyond broad generalizations. In contrast, variable-centered studies provide a combined or averaged estimate of the relationships observed across all individuals in the sample, without explicitly accounting for potential differences in these relationships across subgroups of participants (Morin & Marsh, 2014). Through cluster and profile analysis, we can focus on examining how technologies are integrated and identify exemplary practices within specific teacher profiles. Therefore, from a research perspective, embracing a person-centered approach offers researchers a powerful lens through which to examine complex phenomena, such as technology integration by teachers.

Moreover, from a practice-oriented perspective, policymakers and educational leaders can benefit from a person-centered approach. Since teacher preparation programs should be informed by empirical evidence from research (Darling-Hammond, 2012), understanding the heterogeneity of teachers in the integration of technology in teaching and learning activities would allow to design more tailored training course and support for technology integration. Instead of creating general policies for all teachers, using a person-centered, evidence-based strategy ensures that policies are grounded in real-world data, addressing the actual characteristics of different teacher groups or profiles.

2.2. Factors influencing technology integration

Research has shown that factors such as teachers' characteristics, school environment, and educational systems influence technology integration in the classroom (Bingimlas, 2009; Inan & Lowther, 2010; Joo et al., 2016; Petko et al., 2018; Plomp et al., 2009, pp. 11–16; Taimalu & Luik, 2019). The *will-skill-tool* model (Knezek et al., 2003) postulates that teachers' attitudes, teachers' skills, and the available infrastructure influence the integration of digital technology in classroom activities. While recent studies have found that in more technologically developed countries (Schmitz et al., 2022, 2024a), infrastructural factors (*tools*) do not play a substantial role

anymore, the beliefs (*will*) and competencies (*skills*) of teachers regarding the use of technology for teaching still play a significant role in influencing technology integration in classrooms. This aligns with models of teacher readiness that focus more on teachers' beliefs and skills than on the quality of the infrastructure (e.g., Christensen & Knezek, 2017; Petko et al., 2018).

Research highlights the importance of the *will* dimension in technology integration, showing that teachers' beliefs and attitudes toward technology strongly influence its adoption in classroom practices (Cho & Littenberg-Tobias, 2016; Ertmer, 2005; Ertmer et al., 2012; Hsu, 2016; Levin & Wadman, 2006; Palak & Walls, 2009). Positive beliefs about technology's educational usefulness are critical for effective integration (Ertmer et al., 2012). Teachers who recognize the utility of technology for enhancing teaching and supporting student learning are more inclined to adopt it. This relationship has been observed across various countries and school levels (Scherer et al., 2019; Scherer & Teo, 2019). In line with this, Farjon et al. (2019) found that attitude was the strongest predictor of technology integration, outweighing the importance of tools and skills. Regarding the *skill* dimension, previous studies have confirmed a positive relationship between computer self-efficacy or perceived competence in using technology and technology integration in the classroom (Anderson et al., 2011; Scherer & Siddiq, 2015; Tondeur et al., 2018).

Recently, the *will-skill-tool* model was further extended by including the *pedagogy* dimension, which refers to teachers' confidence in employing instructional strategies when using technology to enrich students' learning experiences (Knezek & Christensen, 2016). The *pedagogy* dimension encompasses the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), as defined in the TPACK framework proposed by Mishra and Koehler (2006, 2008). TPACK underscores the importance of teachers possessing an understanding of how to combine pedagogical knowledge (PK), content knowledge (CK), and technological knowledge (TK) to effectively engage learners in learning activities supported by technology. Several studies have found a positive and significant relationship between TPACK and technology integration in lessons (Guggemos & Seufert, 2021; Schmitz et al., 2024a; Wu, 2013). However, other studies have not confirmed the association between teachers' knowledge and technology use (Schmid et al., 2021; Taimalu & Luik, 2019). Schmid et al. (2021) found that self-reported TPACK was not correlated with the planned use of technology in lessons. Taimalu and Luik (2019) explained the non-significant relationship, suggesting that self-efficacy for using technology might have an indirect rather than a direct effect on the use of technology through some constructs. These conflicting results may be attributed to the type of measure used to assess the constructs related to knowledge and the use of technology. Most of these studies operationalized technology integration as the mere frequency of technology integration. Furthermore, differences may be due to sample size, level of education, pre-service or in-service, and other intervening factors. Therefore, it is difficult to generalize the results, given the unique specificities of each research study.

2.3. Technology integration in Switzerland

In Switzerland, digital literacy is a priority (SEFRI, 2017), with digital competencies integrated across curricula, and computer science courses supporting students' skills. However, PISA 2022 results show Swiss students use digital technologies less than 2 h per day, below the OECD average (OECD, 2023). In addition, several upper secondary school curricula and reforms in Switzerland emphasize constructivist and student-centered approaches to learning. However, it remains unclear how effectively these approaches are taught to teacher trainees and implemented in classrooms (Reinfried, 2004; von Arx, 2014; Koch, 2017). This uncertainty is partly due to Switzerland's federal structure, in which each state of the Swiss Confederation decides independently on its educational policies and practices. In Switzerland, teacher training is highly decentralized, with each state responsible for its own education policies. Teacher education typically takes place at specialized universities of teacher education. While all institutions generally offer courses in teaching methods, educational science, and educational digital technology, the structure and emphasis of these programs may differ from one university to another. Some may place more focus on the pedagogical use of technology, while others may offer more technical training.

Swiss schools also benefit from the pedagogical ICT support to help integrate digital technologies in a meaningful way (Cattaneo et al., 2021, pp. 169–187; Geiss & Röhl, 2024). Pedagogical ICT supporters receive additional training, focusing on both technical integration and pedagogical strategies. This should ensure that digital tools are used to enhance student-centered learning. However, there is significant variation in technology integration practices across states and schools (Schmitz et al., 2024b).

3. Aims and research questions

This study investigates the extent to which different profiles could be identified in terms of teachers' technology integration into teaching practice in upper secondary schools. The investigation seeks to identify distinct profiles among teachers, delineating those who predominantly leverage technology for teacher-directed transmissive teaching methods and those who utilize digital tools for student-centered learning to actively engage students, thereby facilitating the process of knowledge creation. We employed a person-centered analysis approach that makes visible homogeneous groups of teachers. Furthermore, we examined the extent to which teachers' perceived TPACK and beliefs about technology predict profile membership. In summary, we addressed the following research questions.

RQ1. To what extent can different subgroups of upper secondary teachers be identified in terms of technology integration in learning activities according to the ICAP theory?

RQ2. To what extent do perceived TPACK and positive beliefs about technology predict teachers' membership in certain latent profiles?

4. Materials and methods

4.1. Procedure and sample

The study used data from the DigiTraSII project founded by the Swiss National Science Foundation. An online questionnaire was developed and translated from German into French and Italian, with back-translation for accuracy and expert validation. Swiss upper secondary schools' leaders were invited to participate, and teachers received a link to the online questionnaire. After providing informed consent, teachers completed the questionnaire on the Unipark platform. The study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013).

Data were collected in two phases: Zurich canton (September–December 2021) and other cantons (May–August 2022). The initial sample included 2248 teachers from 112 schools. After data cleaning, the final sample included 2088 teachers. Sample details are provided in Table 1.

4.2. Measurements

All measures were self-assessed through an online survey, covering demographics (e.g., gender, age, and language), technology use, beliefs about technology in education, perceived barriers, and school support. We report only the relevant measures.

4.2.1. Technology integration

The ICAP-Technology Scale (ICAP-TS; Antonietti et al., 2023) was used to measure how often teachers integrated technology into four types of learning activities, corresponding to the levels of learner engagement defined by the ICAP theory: passive, active, constructive, and interactive. The ICAP-TS comprises 12 items that are equally distributed among the four dimensions of engagement. Participants were asked to provide responses on a scale ranging from 'Almost never' (1) to 'Nearly every lesson' (5). As our aim was to distinguish different digital technology usage profiles, focusing on quality rather than frequency, and we wanted to consider the within-teacher variability in technology use across the four modes, we computed four scores calculating the relative frequency of using technologies for each specific modality compared to the teacher's average frequency of technology use across all modes. First, we calculated the overall individual mean across all four ICAP dimensions for each teacher (*overall mean*). We then computed the relational score derivation, the deviation of each individual ICAP dimension from the individual total mean. Formally, for a given teacher i and ICAP dimension j , the relational score R_{ij} is:

$$R_{ij} = \text{Dimension Score}_{ij} - \text{Overall Mean}_i$$

To further minimize the presence of information in the data related to the frequency of technology integration, we standardized the relational scores. For each teacher, the mean and standard deviation of their scores across the ICAP modes were used for standardization. We refer to this score as the ICAP-TS relative score.

The objective of this transformation was to isolate information related to qualitative patterns of technology integration, minimizing data noise caused by frequency-related information. Consequently, a teacher who uses digital technologies almost all the time in the classroom and who uses them twice as often in the passive or active modality as in the constructive or interactive modality has the same values as a teacher who uses digital technologies only occasionally but who also uses them twice as often in the passive or active modality as in the constructive or interactive modality. This approach effectively segregated modality-related data from frequency-related data in our analysis.

Table 1
Sample information.

Gender	Male	50.4%
	Female	47.5%
	Diverse	2.1%
Age	Age range	24–73 years
	Mean (Standard deviation)	46.26 (9.90) years
Teaching Experience	Mean (Standard deviation)	15.76 (9.64) years
Language Region	German speaking region	80.3%
	French speaking region	9.3%
	Italian speaking region	10.4%
School Type	General education program	43%
	Vocational education program	39.3%
	General & vocational education program	17.7%
Subject Taught	First Language	5.4%
	Foreign Language	13.4%
	Humanities (e.g., Social Sciences, History)	19.1%
	Sciences (e.g., Math, Physics, Biology)	21%
	Vocational Subjects	14.5%
	Art or Physical Education	4.5%
	Other Subjects (or multiple subjects)	22%

4.2.2. Perceived technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK)

Three items presented by Schmid et al. (2020) were employed to measure perceived TPCK (e.g., “I can apply strategies that combine subject content, technology, and teaching methods in a meaningful way”). The answer options ranged from ‘Totally disagree’ (1) to ‘Totally agree’ (5) (mean = 3.92, SD = 0.816; McDonald’s Omega = 0.869).

4.2.3. Positive beliefs about technology for teaching and learning

Four items were used to assess teachers’ positive beliefs about the use of digital technologies to enhance teaching and learning (e.g., “I can improve the quality of my teaching by using digital technologies”). The answer options ranged from ‘Totally disagree’ (1) to ‘Totally agree’ (5) (mean = 3.33, SD = 0.96, McDonald’s Omega = 0.896).

4.3. Data analysis

To assess the validity of the ICAP-TS, we conducted a confirmatory factor analysis. The chi-squared test, comparative fit index and Tucker-Lewis index (CFI; TLI; good fit ≥ 0.95 ; Brown, 2015), standardized root means squared residual (SRMR; good fit ≤ 0.08 ; Hu & Bentler, 1999), and root means square error of approximation (RMSEA; acceptable fit ≤ 0.08 ; Browne & Cudeck, 1992) were used to examine the fit of the model.

To identify the teachers’ profiles that best described heterogeneity with respect to different modes of integrating technology in learning activities, we performed a latent profile analysis (LPA) using a model that assumed equal variances and covariances across the latent profiles. As observed indicators, we included the four relative ICAP-TS scores we calculated to obtain the relative frequency of digital technology use in the ICAP dimensions.

To identify the number of profiles, we run a series of LPAs starting with one profile and adding profiles incrementally. We compared the LPAs solution based on: the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC) considering that the smaller their values, the better the fit; and the adjusted Lo-Mendell-Rubin (LMR) and the Vuong-Lo-Mendell-Rubin (VLMR) likelihood-ratio tests (LRT). These tests compare models with k profiles against models with $k-1$ profiles. A significant p -value (< 0.05) indicates that the model with k profiles provides a significantly better fit than the model with $k-1$ profiles. We also considered the level of entropy, where values closer to 1 indicated a better classification of teachers into profiles (entropy > 0.70 acceptable; Jung & Wickrama, 2008). The interpretability and size of profiles also inform the decision on the number of profiles (Howard and Hoffman, 2018). Once the best profile solution was selected, we evaluated the precision of the solution in assigning individuals to a profile by comparing the class proportion (CP) with the modal class assignment proportion (mcaP) and estimating the average posterior probability (avePP), as well as estimating the odds of correct classification (OCC). The precision of the latent profile solution is good when the mcaP for each class is included in the 95 percent confidence interval of the CP. Furthermore, to suggest well-separated profiles, the avePP should be 0.70 or higher, and the OCC should be above 5.

After identifying the best latent profile solution, we added TPCK and positive beliefs as predictors of profile membership. Age, teaching experiences, and school type were included as control variables. We used the indirect auxiliary variable approach (“R3STEP”) to estimate the odds ratio coefficients (Asparouhov & Muthén, 2014). The MLR (Maximum Likelihood Robust) estimator was used for robust parameter estimation without missing data. We used Mplus software (version 7.11) and SPSS (version 29) to perform the analyses and address our research questions.

5. Results

5.1. Teachers’ profiles of technology integration

The CFA model showed a good fit. The results demonstrated the reliability and validity of the ICAP-TS. Table 2 reports factors

Table 2
CFA results.

Factor	Indicator	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p	Stand. Estimate
				Lower	Upper			
Passive	P1	0.815	0.0275	0.761	0.869	29.6	<0.001	0.611
	P2	0.962	0.0195	0.924	1	49.3	<0.001	0.892
	P3	1.03	0.0201	0.99	1.069	51.1	<0.001	0.916
Active	A1	1.11	0.0268	1.057	1.162	41.3	<0.001	0.778
	A2	1.175	0.0226	1.13	1.219	52.1	<0.001	0.905
	A3	1.212	0.0234	1.167	1.258	51.9	<0.001	0.904
Constructive	C1	0.988	0.0219	0.945	1.031	45	<0.001	0.827
	C2	1.072	0.0222	1.029	1.116	48.3	<0.001	0.867
	C3	0.883	0.022	0.84	0.926	40.2	<0.001	0.768
Interactive	I1	1.03	0.0207	0.99	1.071	49.9	<0.001	0.888
	I2	0.924	0.0215	0.882	0.966	43	<0.001	0.806
	I3	0.938	0.0209	0.897	0.979	44.9	<0.001	0.83
Fit indices	$\chi^2(48) = 652, p < .001$; CFI = 0.966, TLI = 0.953, RMSEA = 0.0497, 90% confidence interval (CI) [0.0724, 0.0830], SRMR = 0.0497.							

loadings and fit indices.

To answer RQ1, we conducted LPA, and to identify the best fitting model, we specified and estimated a series of LPA models with profiles varying from one to four. We imposed equal variance and covariance constraints across profiles to ensure model parsimony and comparability, while reducing the number of parameters to be estimated. This approach aligns with principles discussed by Bauer and Shanahan (2007) regarding model parsimony and interpretability in person-centered analyses. The model fit information criteria associated with the models with one to four profiles are reported in Table 3. The log-likelihood value improved as the number of profiles increased, which was expected. The 3-profile model had a significantly better log-likelihood than the 2-profile model. Both AIC and BIC decreased as the number of profiles increased. The 3-profile model showed a substantial improvement in both AIC and BIC compared to the 2-profile model. While the 4-profile model had slightly better AIC/BIC values, the improvement was small. The VLMR-LRT and LMR-LRT indicated significant improvement from 2 profiles to 3 profiles ($p < .001$), but the improvement from 3 profiles to 4 profiles, although significant ($p = .003$), was less pronounced. The 2-profile model had the highest entropy, but both the 3-profile and 4-profile models had high entropy, suggesting good classification quality. The 3-profile model's entropy was slightly lower than the 4-profile model but still within a range considered acceptable for LPA (>0.80). We evaluated the size of each profile. The 4-profile model included a profile comprising less than 5% of the total sample, instead the 3-profile model had more balanced profile sizes. Overall, the decision regarding the LPA solution was guided by conceptual considerations, and the interpretability and meaningful size of the profiles (Howard and Hoffman, 2018). The 3-profile model was preferred because it offers a significant improvement in fit over the 2-profile model, while maintaining good classification quality and balanced profile sizes. The 4-profile model, while slightly better in terms of fit indices, added complexity and introduced a small, potentially unstable profile, making the 3-profile model the more parsimonious and interpretable solution. The 3-profile solution was investigated through classification diagnostics. As reported in Table 4, the classification diagnostics showed that the 3-profile model had high classification quality based on AvePP and OCC values. The profiles were well-separated, with a large majority of individuals being correctly assigned to their most likely class. The final three profiles are shown in Fig. 1. All the z-standardized mean scores, standard errors and confidence intervals are reported in Table 5.

Profile 1 ($N = 896$) represents teachers who predominantly integrate technology to support passive learning activities, such as informing, demonstrating, and explaining content and knowledge. Specifically, these teachers integrate technology 1.484 standard deviations more often than their average across all forms of technology integration. This suggests that teachers in Profile 1 rely significantly more on technology for passive learning experiences, such as presentations or videos, where students are more likely to be passive recipients of information rather than active participants. Conversely, their use of technology for active, constructive and interactive learning activities falls below their average. Accordingly, the teachers in Profile 1 were referred to as *digital presenters*.

Profile 2 ($N = 979$) included the largest number of teachers. Teachers in this profile demonstrate a mixed pattern of technology integration. They use technology 0.792 standard deviations above their average for supporting passive learning activities. Additionally, their technology integration to support active learning activities is 0.846 standard deviations above their average, suggesting these teachers also let students use technology for writing down and recording knowledge imparted, practicing, and solving simple tasks. However, in contrast, their use of technology for constructive and interactive learning activities falls below their average, indicating less frequent activities that require students to use technology to construct knowledge actively or interact with their peers and instructors through technology. This profile was labeled *digital activators*.

Profile 3 ($N = 213$) included the lowest number of teachers. They used technology more frequently to support active and constructive learning activities than to support passive activities relative to their overall patterns of technology integration. Specifically, the teachers in this profile integrate technology in active learning activities 0.544 standard deviations above their personal average across all types of integration. Similarly, they engage in constructive learning activities 0.557 standard deviations above their average. Constructive activities require that students use technology to acquire new knowledge, solve complex problems, and produce something new. Accordingly, teachers in Profile 3 were labeled *digital constructivists*. Among the three profiles, *digital constructivists* were teachers who reported integrating technology to support interactive learning activities with a higher relative frequency than those in Profiles 1 and 2. Indeed, the use of technology for interactive learning is slightly below their personal average, at -0.108 standard deviations.

Table 3

Relative model fit indices for the four latent profile models.

# Profiles	# Parameters	LL	LL replicated	AIC	BIC	VLMR-LRT	LMR-LRT	Entropy	Profile Size
1	6	-7990.820	Yes	15993.639	16027.503		-		2088
2	11	-7016.569	Yes	14055.139	14117.222	1948.501, $p < .001$	1898.819, $p < .001$	0.956	1841; 247
3	16	-6247.469	Yes	12526.937	12566.407	1538.20, $p < .001$	1498.98, $p < .001$.865	979; 896; 213
4	21	-5881.060	Yes	11804.120	11922.643	732.82, $p = .003$	714.13, $p = .003$	0.909	972; 836; 196; 84

Note. LL = Log-likelihood; AIC = Akaike Information Criterion; BIC = Bayesian Information Criterion; VLMR-LRT = Vuong-Lo-Mendell-Rubin Likelihood Ratio Test; LMR-LRT = Lo-Mendell-Rubin Adjusted Likelihood Ratio Test; Bold values indicate the suggested model.

Table 4
Classification diagnostics for the three-profile model.

	N	CP (95 CI)	mcaP	avePP	OCC
Profile 1	896	42.63% (40.6%, 44.6%)	42.91%	0.926	13.71
Profile 2	979	47.18% (45.2%, 49.1%)	46.89%	0.942	14.63
Profile 3	213	10.18% (8.9%, 11.5%)	10.20%	0.973	37.46

Note. CP = Class Proportion; CI = Confidence Interval; Mcap = Modal Class Assignment Proportion; Avepp = Average Posterior Probability; OCC = Odds of Correct Classification.

Fig. 1. Three-profile solution for teachers' technology integration showing z-standardized mean scores for the different ICAP components of profile members on the y-axis.

Table 5
Mean scores, standard errors and confidence intervals for each profile.

	Profile		
	Profile 1	Profile 2	Profile 3
Passive Mean score (standard error)	1.484 (0.010)	0.792 (0.026)	-0.992 (0.048)
Active Mean score (standard error)	-0.427 (0.033)	0.846 (0.019)	0.544 (0.077)
Constructive Mean score (standard error)	-0.426 (0.022)	-0.376 (0.029)	0.557 (0.057)
Interactive Mean score (standard error)	-0.633 (0.026)	-1.262 (0.017)	-0.108 (0.080)
Passive Confidence Interval	1.464–1.504	0.741–0.843	-1.086–-0.898
Active Confidence Interval	-0.492–-0.362	0.809–0.883	0.393–0.695
Constructive Confidence Interval	-0.469–-0.383	-0.433–-0.319	0.445–0.669
Interactive Confidence Interval	-0.684–-0.582	-1.295–-1.229	-0.265 – 0.049

8.2. Relationship between TPCK and beliefs and teachers' profile

We reported the correlations between the ICAP-TS relative scores and the TPCK and beliefs variables (Table 6). TPCK correlates positively with beliefs and the Active score but negatively with the Interactive score. Beliefs negatively correlate with the Interactive score. We used the R3STEP method to estimate how TPCK and positive beliefs influence the likelihood of belonging to a particular profile membership, controlling for age, teaching experiences, and school type. Multinomial logistic regression was used to estimate regression coefficients, standard errors, odds ratio of belonging to each profile (Table 7). Comparing Profile 1 (digital presenters) with

Table 6
Correlations table.

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Passive	-				
2. Active	-0.447**	-			
3. Constructive	-0.462**	-0.216**	-		
4. Interactive	-0.192**	-0.473**	-0.184**	-	
5. TPCK	0.001	0.066**	0.032	-0.115**	-
6. Positive beliefs	0.043	0.019	-0.021	-0.054*	0.398**

Note. *p < .05; **p < .01; ***p < .001.

Profile 2 (*digital activators*), higher TPCK is associated with a higher likelihood of being in Profile 1 compared to Profile 2. Instead, beliefs do not strongly differentiate between Profile 1 and Profile 2. Comparing Profile 3 (*digital constructivists*) with Profile 2, TPCK and beliefs do not significantly differentiate between Profile 3 and Profile 2. When comparing Profile 3 with Profile 1, results revealed that teachers with higher TPCK and beliefs are more likely to be in Profile 1 than in Profile 3. Overall TPCK is a strong predictor of profile membership. Higher TPCK is associated with a greater likelihood of being in Profile 1 than Profile 2 or 3. Beliefs also influence profile membership. Teachers with higher beliefs are more likely to be in Profile 1 than 3, but the effect is weaker between Profile 1 and 2. Age, teaching experience, and school type do not significantly differentiate between the profiles.

6. Discussion

Technology has been integrated into teaching for over three decades. However, the way teachers use it is not consistent, as demonstrated by several studies that have identified different patterns of technology integration (Donnelly et al., 2011; Graves & Bowers, 2018; Hadley & Sheingold, 1993; Lohr et al., 2021; Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al., 2021). Some teachers primarily use technology to support presentations and traditional direct teaching, while others use it mostly for activities that actively engage students in the learning process, such as practicing, exercising, or solving problems. In higher education, technology can also be a means of supporting collaborative learning activities (Lohr et al., 2021). There is a shortage of updated data on technology use in secondary school teaching, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic, which likely accelerated classroom technology adoption. During the pandemic, many teachers quickly developed digital competencies and strategies to actively engage students in online learning (König et al., 2020). Research indicates that teachers learned to adapt by using technology to facilitate more interactive and student-centered activities, despite the challenges posed by the sudden shift to remote teaching (Poza et al., 2021). In addition to examining the frequency of technology use, it is essential to explore teachers' patterns of technology integration to gain a deeper understanding of how they use technologies to support classroom activities. We have employed individual relative scores that reveal how each teacher integrates technology across various ICAP learning activities, compared to their own average integration patterns across all ICAP modes. This method allows us to identify specific patterns in teachers' technology use, independently of the overall frequency, highlighting the distinct ways in which they apply technology to enhance different types of learning.

Latent profile analysis identified three profiles: *digital presenters*, who primarily integrate technology in passive learning activities (e.g., using technology to present learning content) relative to their own average use across all learning activities; *digital activators*, who use technology more frequently for passive and active (e.g., asking students to utilize technology for practicing, exercising, and solving simple tasks based on acquired knowledge) learning activities compared to their other uses; and *digital constructivists*, who focus on using technology for active and constructive activities relative to their overall technology integration patterns. Teachers in Profile 1 (*digital presenters*) may also integrate technology in student-centered activities, such as active and constructive learning activities, but they do so less frequently compared to passive learning activities. Similarly, teachers in the Profile 2 (*digital activators*) may also integrate technology in constructive activities, but not as often as they rely on active and passive learning activities.

In terms of distribution, most teachers belonged to Profile 1 (*digital presenters*) and Profile 2 (*digital activators*). Very few teachers were present in Profile 3 (*digital constructivists*). These findings align with previous studies that have highlighted differences in technology integration across classroom activities among teachers (Graves & Bowers, 2018; Lohr et al., 2021; Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al., 2021). However, in contrast to previous studies that found a similar distribution of teachers in the different profiles, in our sample, teachers were not equally distributed. Indeed, we found a lower proportion of teachers in the *digital constructivist* profile ($N = 213$) than in the other two profiles (*digital presenters* $N = 896$; *digital activators* $N = 979$). The small number of teachers in the *digital constructivist* profile could be due to several reasons.

Table 7

Results of the multinomial logistic regression predicting profile membership.

Comparison	Variable	B	SE	Odds Ratio	<i>p</i>
Profile 1 vs. 2	TPCK	0.275	0.071	1.317	0.000
	Beliefs	0.086	0.063	1.090	0.173
	Age	0.009	0.008	1.009	0.281
	Teaching experience	-0.007	0.009	0.993	0.383
	General education ^a	0.203	0.112	1.224	0.071
Profile 3 vs. 2	TPCK	-0.020	0.120	0.980	0.865
	Beliefs	-0.145	0.100	0.865	0.149
	Age	0.001	0.013	1.001	0.920
	Teaching experience	0.010	0.013	1.010	0.468
	General education ^a	0.064	0.164	1.066	0.696
Profile 3 vs. 1	TPCK	-0.296	0.122	0.744	0.016
	Beliefs	-0.231	0.102	0.794	0.023
	Age	-0.008	0.013	0.992	0.568
	Teaching experience	0.017	0.014	1.017	0.206
	General education ^a	-0.138	0.169	0.871	0.413

Note.

^a Schools offering vocational education programs served as the reference group. TPCK = Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. SE = Standard Error.

First, teachers could encounter obstacles in the implementation of constructive and interactive activities supported by technology (e.g., little time available, heterogeneous classes, and lack of adequate teaching materials) rather than other type of activities. Indeed, constructive and interactive activities supported by technology tend to occur less frequently than passive or active ones, likely due to their more time-consuming nature. Activities that require students to actively construct knowledge or engage with peers often demand significantly more class time to implement effectively, making them less practical in the context of limited instructional hours.

Second, the teachers perceived the software and technologies available to them as particularly suitable and effective for an approach to teaching that is more based on transmission and practice than on the implementation of constructive and interactive activities. Or digital technologies are not appropriate for the specific content that needs to be taught.

Third, passive learning activities are reported more frequently than other types of activities because they continue to play an important role. Indeed, teachers often rely on methods such as digital presentations to introduce tasks or concepts that students later engage with through constructive or interactive activities. This passive stage is essential in providing context, setting up learning goals, and clarifying instructions before students proceed to more cognitively demanding tasks.

Comparing our results with those of previous studies is challenging because technology integration has been operationalized in many ways (Consoli et al., 2023). Previous research has often measured merely the frequency of technology use, whereas our research focused on patterns of technology integration across different activities. Specifically, our classification of teachers into different technology integration profiles was based on the ratio between the performance of different activities supported by technology (i.e., ICAP-TS relative score) and not on the measure of the absolute frequency of technology integration (in general or across different activities). This study differs from the previous research that measured technology integration using the ICAP-TS in the same context (Antonietti et al., 2023). The previous study focused on absolute frequencies of technology use across learning activities, without employing latent profile analysis. It only reported descriptive means of how often technology was integrated into ICAP learning activities, providing a less nuanced view compared to the current approach.

It is interesting to compare our results with those of Lohr et al. (2021) as they also identified three profiles (i.e., powerpointers, clickers, and digital pros) that are close to our profiles in terms of technology use. Despite this commonality, Lohr et al.'s study involved teachers in higher education and did not calculate relative scores, allowing teachers' frequency of technology use to influence on their profile membership. Moreover, the teachers in their sample were almost equally distributed across the three profiles, and even the digital pros (comparable to those we labeled *digital constructivists*) were well represented. In our sample of upper secondary teachers, relatively few reported integrating technologies to support constructive learning activities more frequently than active and passive activities. However, it may be possible that there are teachers who frequently integrate technology into constructive and even interactive activities. Since our analysis did not focus on absolute frequency, such teachers may not have been detected. Instead, by using relative scores, we were able to identify differences in patterns of technology integration that allowed us to assess the extent to which certain activities were implemented relatively to others, regardless of the overall frequency of technology use. Furthermore, differences between the study by Lohr et al. and our study could be attributed to differences in educational settings. It might be possible that teachers in higher education design activities that require students to actively use technology to discover, make inferences, solve complex problems, and consequently generate new knowledge more often than upper secondary school teachers. This does not imply that constructive activities are not supported in upper secondary schools, but rather that teachers do not fully exploit the potential of technology to facilitate such activities.

To understand which factors may explain the differences among the three profiles identified, we investigated whether perceived TPCK and positive beliefs about technology could predict membership in one profile rather than another. We chose these factors based on previous literature highlighting how TPCK and beliefs are crucial factors in explaining technology use (Anderson et al., 2011; Scherer & Siddiq, 2015; Tondeur et al., 2018). The results showed that TPCK and positive belief have a role in predicting profile membership. The comparison of Profiles 1 and 2 revealed that teachers with high perceived TPCK were more likely to be members of the *digital presenters'* profile than *digital activators*. The result is not consistent with previous studies on the TPACK framework, according to which TPCK is associated with more advanced technology integration (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Further comparison of *digital activators* and *digital constructivists* showed that the TPCK variable had no statistically significant effect. A possible explanation for these results is that the former comparison might overestimate their TPCK due to the Dunning–Kruger effect.

Another possible explanation for the results of the TPCK effect may lie in the measurement of this variable itself. The TPCK variable measured the teachers' perceived knowledge of how they effectively use technology to achieve pedagogical goals and teach specific content. However, these pedagogical goals and strategies may differ among teachers in the three profiles. For instance, *digital presenters*, who primarily use technologies to support transmissive strategies, might find technology integration in passive learning activities more aligned with their goals and content. In contrast, *digital activators* and *constructivists*, whose pedagogical aims involve more active and constructivist strategies, may encounter greater complexity in understanding how to use technology to enhance these approaches. This variation could explain the differences in the ability of TPCK to predict profile membership. However, the TPCK variable we employed did not provide fine-grained information on the pedagogical goals and strategies of the teachers. Measuring the type of general pedagogical approach and strategies next to TPCK would be worthwhile. Indeed, the teachers' pedagogical approach could explain the differences in TPCK and technology use (Di Blas et al., 2014; Petko, 2012).

Furthermore, Niederhauser and Stoddart (2001) found a relationship between instructional perspective (teacher-directed vs. learner-centered) and the type of software they use in instruction (drill-and-practice software vs. open-ended software), suggesting that teachers who align with transmission-based instruction are more likely to choose drill-and-practice software, and teachers who align with learner-centered and constructivist perspectives tend to choose more open-ended software. This is further evidence supporting the importance of considering teachers' pedagogical approach when investigating technology integration. Therefore, the pedagogical dimension should be further investigated using measures beyond TPCK, as teachers' pedagogical approach might better

explain the differences between teachers' profiles rather than self-assessed TPCK.

Concerning the role of teachers' beliefs about technology in teaching and learning, positive beliefs were a predictor of teachers' membership. The comparison of Profiles 1 and 3 revealed that teachers with high positive beliefs about technology were more likely to be members of the *digital presenters* profile than *digital constructivists*. This result is surprising, as we expected that teachers who balanced technology integration more toward active and constructive activities, rather than passive ones (i.e., the *digital constructivists*) would exhibit the highest levels of positive attitude toward technology use. These findings can be interpreted in many ways. For example, it is possible that *digital presenters* are more technology enthusiasts and have a more technocentric (or tool-centered) approach than *digital constructivists*, whereas *digital constructivists* have a more pedagogy-centered approach and are therefore more aware of the fact that technology can sometimes enhance pedagogy and sometimes hinder it (and are thus more critical toward the integration of technologies in classroom activities). Moreover, *digital constructivists* may have lower positive beliefs about the effectiveness of technology compared to *digital presenter*, as they tend to be more critical of its limitations, particularly when implementing constructive and interactive learning activities supported by technology. These limitations may become more apparent to them because they rely more heavily on technology for such activities. In contrast, *digital presenters* focusing more on passive activities face these limitations to a lesser extent. This suggests that the perceived usefulness of technology could depend on the type of pedagogical activities being implemented, with beliefs about technology's effectiveness varying according to how it supports different teaching strategies.

6.1. Limitations

A key limitation is the reliance on teachers' self-reports, without evaluating students' actual technology use. Additionally, the ICAP theory assumes certain tasks elicit specific cognitive engagement, but observable behaviors may not fully reflect cognitive processes, a limitation of the theory itself. Nevertheless, since this study aimed to classify different technology-supported learning activities facilitated by teachers and not by students, the ICAP theory effectively serves this goal. Future research should examine the alignment between teachers' reports and students' actual technology engagement.

Another debated aspect of ICAP theory is its assumed hierarchy of engagement levels. This study, however, does not aim to validate such a hierarchy or rank levels but rather to capture the diversity of technology-supported learning activities facilitated by teachers. For example, some teachers integrated technology across various activities, showing diverse usage patterns, while others focused on a single type of learning activity.

Moreover, as the effectiveness of learning activities depends on the content and the learning objectives, some subjects may be better suited to certain types of learning activities than others. However, this study could not include the subject variable as control, as many teachers taught multiple disciplines, making subject grouping unfeasible.

We acknowledge that ICAP theory has certain limitations and simplifies the complex dynamics of student learning. However, its descriptive utility in classifying technology-supported learning activities in this study remains valuable since the focus of this study is on how teachers integrate technology rather than directly measuring student engagement with technologies.

Another limitation of our study is the reliance on self-report TPCK and beliefs, which may be biased by social desirability, leading teachers to overestimate their actual abilities or effectiveness in technology integration (Drummond & Sweeney, 2017). Future studies should incorporate objective measures or use multiple methods to improve accuracy.

A further limitation concerns sample representativeness. The voluntary participation may have led to self-selection bias. Language differences could also influence the results due to varying educational contexts. While the large and diverse sample enhances representativeness, the findings should be generalized with caution. Furthermore, as Switzerland's advanced educational infrastructure may not represent contexts with differing technological access or socio-economic conditions, the findings may not apply to less-resourced educational systems. Future research in diverse settings is necessary to determine whether similar patterns of technology integration and teacher profiles emerge in varying contexts.

Finally, a limitation from a statistical perspective is the use of equal variance and covariance constraints in the LPA. While this simplifies the model, it may not fully capture the variability between profiles.

6.2. Implications

Our study contributes to the literature by identifying distinct teacher profiles based on technology integration thus enriching our understanding of technology use in education and it highlights the role of TPCK and beliefs in shaping these profiles. However, further research is needed to explore whether pedagogical strategies may be stronger predictors of profile membership than TPCK and beliefs.

The identification of different technology integration profiles, each with varying relationships to TPCK and beliefs, challenges existing models like the *will-skill-tool* model, which treats overall technology use as a single dependent variable and overlooks the complexity of how will, skills, and tools relate to distinct patterns of technology integration. Future research should delve into these profiles, exploring their characteristics in terms of knowledge, beliefs, and pedagogical approaches to better understand how these factors shape technology integration.

Using the ICAP model to investigate technology integration by analyzing the ratios of different ICAP modes adopted by teachers, rather than just the overall frequency of technology use, is particularly useful for large-scale surveys aiming to provide a general overview of technology integration. However, future studies should integrate both the frequency and quality of technology use, as both dimensions are important for a comprehensive understanding of technology integration practices.

Regarding the TPACK model, our study highlighted how there might be different results in the relationship between TPACK and

technology integration when the focus is on the quality of technology integration (i.e., different profiles of technology use) rather than on the frequency.

From a practical standpoint, our study offers valuable insights for educators, school administrators, and policymakers. By recognizing distinct teacher profiles associated with different levels of TPACK and beliefs, institutions can tailor professional development to meet specific needs. This allows for more effective, targeted interventions, improving technology integration in classrooms. For example, digital presenters may benefit from training that promotes active and constructive learning approaches using technology, rather than just for passive presentations. Such data-driven professional development can enhance overall teaching effectiveness.

7. Conclusion

This study identifies three teacher profiles in Swiss upper secondary schools: *digital presenters*, *digital activators*, and *digital constructivists*, with the latter group being smaller. High TPCK and positive beliefs predicted *digital presenters* membership. The interpretation of these results remains speculative, but it is possible that teachers' pedagogical approaches influence their perception of TPCK, beliefs about technology, and how they integrate technology into their teaching. Future research should explore whether factors such as pedagogical approaches and strategies influence how teachers integrate technology, as well as their TPCK and beliefs about technology. It is possible that pedagogical approaches predict technology integration patterns, while TPCK and beliefs might better predict the frequency rather than the quality of technology use. Moreover, our study underscores the importance of considering how technology is integrated in support of learning activities, not just its frequency of use, when studying technology integration in education. In this direction, there is still a substantial amount of research to be done, especially to investigate which pedagogical approach is related to different types of technology-supported activities in secondary schools.

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chiara Antonietti: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tessa Consoli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Maria-Luisa Schmitz:** Writing – review & editing. **Alberto Cattaneo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Philipp Gonon:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Dominik Petko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare. All procedures performed in this study were in accordance with the 1964 Helsinki declaration, and the ethical standards of the Swiss Academy of Social Sciences and Humanities. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declarations of interest

None.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (grant number 187277)

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Anderson, S. E., Groulx, J. G., & Maninger, R. M. (2011). Relationships among preservice teachers' technology-related abilities, beliefs, and intentions to use technology in their future classrooms. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 45(3), 321–338. <https://doi.org/10.2190/EC.45.3.d>
- Antonietti, C., Cattaneo, A., & Amenduni, F. (2022). Can teachers' digital competence influence technology acceptance in vocational education? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 132, Article 107266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107266>
- Antonietti, C., Schmitz, M. L., Consoli, T., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2023). Development and validation of the ICAP Technology Scale to measure how teachers integrate technology into learning activities. *Computers & Education*, 192, Article 104648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104648>
- Bauer, D. J., & Shanahan, M. J. (2007). Modeling complex interactions: Person-centered and variable-centered approaches. In T. Little, J. Bovaird, & N. Card (Eds.), *Modeling ecological and contextual effects in longitudinal studies of human development* (pp. 255–283). Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Bingimlas, K. A. (2009). Barriers to the successful integration of ICT in teaching and learning environments: A review of the literature. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 5(3), 235–245. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ejmste/75275>
- Browne, M. W., & Cudeck, R. (1992). Alternative ways of assessing model fit. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 21(2), 230–258.

- Callahan, W. (2001). Technology as facilitator of quality education: A model. In C. Montgomerie, & J. Viteli (Eds.), *Proceedings of ED-MEDIA 2001 World Conference on educational multimedia, Hypermedia & Telecommunications* (pp. 225–227). Norfolk, VA USA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). <https://www.learnlib.org/primary/p/8292/>.
- Cattaneo, A. A., Antonietti, C., & Rauseo, M. (2022). How digitalised are vocational teachers? Assessing digital competence in vocational education and looking at its underlying factors. *Computers & Education*, 176, Article 104358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104358>
- Cattaneo, A. A., Bonini, L., & Rauseo, M. (2021). The “digital facilitator”: An extended profile to manage the digital transformation of Swiss vocational schools. *Digital transformation of learning Organizations*.
- Chi, M. T., Adams, J., Bogusch, E. B., Bruchok, C., Kang, S., Lancaster, M., Levy, R., Li, N., McElldoon, K. L., Stump, G. S., Wylie, R., Xu, D., & Yaghmourian, D. L. (2018). Translating the ICAP theory of cognitive engagement into practice. *Cognitive Science*, 42(6), 1777–1832. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12626>
- Chi, M. T., & Wylie, R. (2014). The ICAP framework: Linking cognitive engagement to active learning outcomes. *Educational Psychologist*, 49(4), 219–243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2014.965823>
- Cho, V., & Littenberg-Tobias, J. (2016). Digital devices and teaching the whole student: Developing and validating an instrument to measure educators' attitudes and beliefs. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 64, 643–659. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-016-9441-x>
- Christensen, R., & Knezek, G. (2017). Validating a mobile learning readiness survey: Assessing teachers' dispositions toward adoption. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 33(4), 148–159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2017.1347536>
- Consoli, T., Désiron, J., & Cattaneo, A. (2023). What is “technology integration” and how is it measured in K-12 education? A systematic review of survey instruments from 2010 to 2021. *Computers & Education*, 197, Article 104742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104742>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2012). *Powerful teacher education: Lessons from exemplary programs*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Di Blas, N., Fiore, A., Mainetti, L., Vergallo, R., & Paolini, P. (2014). A portal of educational resources: Providing evidence for matching pedagogy with technology. *Research in Learning Technology*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3402/rlt.v22.22906>
- Donnelly, D., McGarr, O., & O'Reilly, J. (2011). A framework for teachers' integration of ICT into their classroom practice. *Computers & Education*, 57(2), 1469–1483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2011.02.014>
- Drummond, A., & Sweeney, T. (2017). Can an objective measure of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) supplement existing TPACK measures? *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 48(4), 928–939. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12473>
- Ertmer, P. A. (2005). Teacher pedagogical beliefs: The final frontier in our quest for technology integration? *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 53(4), 25–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02504683>
- Ertmer, P. A., Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T., Sadik, O., Sendurur, E., & Sendurur, P. (2012). Teacher beliefs and technology integration practices: A critical relationship. *Computers & Education*, 59(2), 423–435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.02.001>
- Farjon, D., Smits, A., Voogt, J., Farjon, D., Smits, A., & Voogt, J. (2019). Technology integration of pre-service teachers explained by attitudes and beliefs, competency, access, and experience. *Computers & Education*, 130, 81–93.
- Fütterer, T., Scheiter, K., Cheng, X., & Stürmer, K. (2022). Quality beats frequency? Investigating students' effort in learning when introducing technology in classrooms. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 69, Article 102042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2022.102042>
- Geiss, M., & Röhl, T. (2024). Working at the frontier: Swiss educational information and communication technology coordinators as mediators and intermediaries of the digital transformation. *Research in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00345237241242989>
- Graves, K. E., & Bowers, A. J. (2018). Toward a typology of technology-using teachers in the “new digital divide”: A latent class analysis of the NCES fast response survey system teachers' use of educational technology in us public schools, 2009 (FRSS 95). *Teachers College Record*, 120(8), 1–42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01614681181200080>
- Guggemos, J., & Seufert, S. (2021). Teaching with and teaching about technology—Evidence for professional development of in-service teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106613>
- Hadley, M., & Sheingold, K. (1993). Commonalities and distinctive patterns in teachers' integration of computers. *American Journal of Education*, 101, 261–315. <https://doi.org/10.1086/444044>
- Howard, M. C., & Hoffman, M. E. (2018). Variable-centered, person-centered, and person-specific approaches: Where theory meets the method. *Organizational Research Methods*, 21(4), 846–876. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10944281177440>
- Hsu, P. S. (2016). Examining current beliefs, practices and barriers about technology integration: A case study. *TechTrends*, 60, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-015-0014-3>
- Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55.
- Inan, F. A., & Lowther, D. L. (2010). Factors affecting technology integration in K-12 classrooms: A path model. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 58, 137–154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-009-9132-y>
- Jeong, H., & Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2016). Seven affordances of computer-supported collaborative learning: How to support collaborative learning? How can technologies help? *Educational Psychologist*, 51(2), 247–265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2016.1158654>
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2013). Cooperation and the use of technology. In D. Jonassen, & M. Driscoll (Eds.), *Handbook of research on educational communications and technology* (pp. 777–803). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410609519>
- Joo, Y. J., Lim, K. Y., & Kim, N. H. (2016). The effects of secondary teachers' technostress on the intention to use technology in South Korea. *Computers & Education*, 95, 114–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2015.12.004>
- Juuti, K., Kervinen, A., & Loukomes, A. (2022). Quality over frequency in using digital technology: Measuring the experienced functional use. *Computers & Education*, 176, Article 104361.
- Knezek, G., & Christensen, R. (2016). Extending the will, skill, tool model of technology integration: Adding pedagogy as a new model construct. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 28(3), 307–325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12528-016-9120-2>
- Knezek, G., Christensen, R., & Fluke, R. (2003). Testing a will, skill, tool model of technology integration. *American educational research association (AERA) Annual meeting 2003, Chicago, United States of America* [Conference presentation] <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED475762.pdf>.
- Koch, A. F. (2017). Pedagogical content knowledge and constructivist teaching: A Hot potato's last straw in Swiss science classrooms. In *Cognitive and affective aspects in science education research: Selected Papers from the ESERA 2015 Conference* (pp. 87–100). Springer International Publishing.
- König, J., Jäger-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: Teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 608–622. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1809650>
- Levin, T., & Wadmany, R. (2006). Teachers' beliefs and practices in technology-based classrooms: A developmental view. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 39(2), 157–181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2006.10782478>
- Lohr, A., Stadler, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., Chernikova, O., Sailer, M., Fischer, F., & Sailer, M. (2021). On powerpointers, clickerers, and digital pros: Investigating the initiation of digital learning activities by teachers in higher education. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 119, Article 106715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106715>
- Mama, M., & Hennessy, S. (2013). Developing a typology of teacher beliefs and practices concerning classroom use of ICT. *Computers & Education*, 68, 380–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.05.022>
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017–1054. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9620.2006.00684.x>
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2008). Introducing technological pedagogical content knowledge. *American educational research association (AERA) Annual meeting 2008*. New York: United States of America [Conference presentation].
- Morin, A. J. S., & Marsh, H. W. (2014). Disentangling shape from level effects in person-centered analyses: An illustration based on university teachers' multidimensional profiles of effectiveness. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 22(1), 39–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705511.2014.919825>

- Niederhauser, D. S., & Stoddart, T. (2001). Teachers' instructional perspectives and use of educational software. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(1), 15–31.
- Ninković, S., Florić, O. K., & Momčilović, M. (2023). Multilevel analysis of the effects of principal support and innovative school climate on the integration of technology in learning activities. *Computers & Education*, 202, Article 104833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104833>
- OECD. (2015). Students, computers and learning: Making the connection. *Pisa*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239555-en>
- OECD. (2023). *PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The State of Learning and Equity in education*, PISA. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881-en>
- Palak, D., & Walls, R. T. (2009). Teachers' beliefs and technology practices: A mixed-methods approach. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 41(4), 417–441. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2009.10782537>
- Petko, D. (2012). Teachers' pedagogical beliefs and their use of digital media in classrooms: Sharpening the focus of the 'will, skill, tool' model and integrating teachers' constructivist orientations. *Computers & Education*, 58(4), 1351–1359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2011.12.013>
- Petko, D., Cantieni, A., & Prasse, D. (2017). Perceived quality of educational technology matters: A secondary analysis of students' ICT use, ICT-related attitudes, and PISA 2012 test scores. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 54(8), 1070–1091.
- Petko, D., Prasse, D., & Cantieni, A. (2018). The interplay of school readiness and teacher readiness for educational technology integration: A structural equation model. *Computers in the Schools*, 35(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07380569.2018.1428007>
- Plomp, T., Pelgrum, W. J., & Carstens, R. (2009). *Technical overview of SITES 2006. Second information technology in education study: SITES 2006 technical report*.
- Pozo, J. I., Pérez Echeverría, M. P., Cabellos, B., & Sánchez, D. L. (2021). Teaching and learning in times of COVID-19: Uses of digital technologies during school lockdowns. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 656776.
- Reinfried, S. (2004). Do curriculum reforms affect classroom teaching in geography? The case study of Switzerland. *International Research in Geographical & Environmental Education*, 13(3), 239–250.
- Sailer, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., & Fischer, F. (2021). Contextual facilitators for learning activities involving technology in higher education: The Cb-model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 121, Article 106794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106794>
- Scherer, R., & Siddiq, F. (2015). Revisiting teachers' computer self-efficacy: A differentiated view on gender differences. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 53, 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.06.038>
- Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Tondeur, J. (2019). The technology acceptance model (TAM): A meta-analytic structural equation modeling approach to explaining teachers' adoption of digital technology in education. *Computers & Education*, 128, 13–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.09.009>
- Scherer, R., & Teo, T. (2019). Unpacking teachers' intentions to integrate technology: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 27, 90–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.03.001>
- Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2020). Developing a short assessment instrument for Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK. xs) and comparing the factor structure of an integrative and a transformative model. *Computers & Education*, 157, Article 103967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103967>
- Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2021). Self-reported technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) of pre-service teachers in relation to digital technology use in lesson plans. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, Article 106586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106586>
- Schmitz, M. L., Antonietti, C., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2022). When barriers are not an issue: Tracing the relationship between hindering factors and technology use in secondary schools across Europe. *Computers & Education*, 179, Article 104411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104411>
- Schmitz, M. L., Consoli, T., Antonietti, C., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2024a). Why do some teachers teach media literacy while others do not? Exploring predictors along the “will, skill, tool, pedagogy” model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 151, Article 108004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.108004>
- Schmitz, M. L., Consoli, T., Antonietti, C., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2024b). Examining 21st century skills in BYOD schools: From programs to practice. *Zeitschrift für Bildungsforschung*, 14(2), 299–322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s35834-024-00425-w>
- SEFRI. (2017). *Aktionsplan Digitalisierung: Bildung und Forschung sollen gestärkt werden* [Digitization Action Plan: education and research are to be strengthened]. <https://www.sbf.admin.ch/sbf/en/home/eri-policy/eri-21-24/cross-cutting-themes/digitalisation-eri/Action%20for%20digitalisation%20in%20the%20ERI%20sector.html>.
- Stegmann, K. (2020). Effekte digitalen Lernens auf den Wissens- und Kompetenzerwerb in der Schule. Eine Integration metaanalytischer Befunde. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogik*, 66(2), 174–190. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:25790>
- Taimalu, M., & Luik, P. (2019). The impact of beliefs and knowledge on the integration of technology among teacher educators: A path analysis. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 79, 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.12.012>
- Tamim, R. M., Bernard, R. M., Borokhovski, E., Abrami, P. C., & Schmid, R. F. (2011). What forty years of research says about the impact of technology on learning: A second-order meta-analysis and validation study. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(1), 4–28.
- Tondeur, J., Aesaert, K., Prestridge, S., & Consuegra, E. (2018). A multilevel analysis of what matters in the training of pre-service teacher's ICT competencies. *Computers & Education*, 122, 32–42.
- Valtonen, T., López-Pernas, S., Saqr, M., Vartiainen, H., Sointu, E. T., & Tedre, M. (2022). The nature and building blocks of educational technology research. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 128, Article 107123.
- von Arx, M. (2014). Constructivist approaches to teaching. In H. E. Fischer, P. Labudde, K. Neumann, & J. Viiri (Eds.), *Quality of instruction in physics: Comparing Finland, Switzerland and Germany* (pp. 177–192). Waxmann.
- Wekerle, C., Daumiller, M., & Kollar, I. (2020). Using digital technology to promote higher education learning: The importance of different learning activities and their relations to learning outcomes. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2020.1799455>
- World Medical Association. (2013). World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*, 310(20), 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.281053>
- Wu, Y. T. (2013). Research trends in technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) research: A review of empirical studies published in selected journals from 2002 to 2011. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 44(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2012.01349.x>
- Yukhymenko-Lescroart, M. A., Donnelly-Hermosillo, D. F., Cowan, C. C., & Berrett, B. D. (2021). A latent profile analysis of university faculty subtypes for mobile technology integration. *Computers and Education Open*, 2, Article 100052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2021.100052>